

Supplementary Material 5

Detailed description of performing breast ultrasound

1. In the armpit it is necessary to visualize the humeral head, then moving down from the humeral head between the pectoral muscles and the back, and localization of changes in relation to the level of the pectoral muscles (major and minor) is visible.
2. Probe rotation to repeat the test (internal test control) applies visibility to the armpit and mammary gland.
3. It is worth learning how to pass "en block" between the armpit and the mammary gland, so as not to miss any fragment of the gland (especially important at Spence's tail), we direct the probe from the armpit to the border of the gland.
4. Moving the probe in a pendulum: up-down, down-up, and "overlap" that one movement overlaps the other, and right-left, left-right, to minimize the risk of overlooking significant changes.
5. Describing the results according to the BIRADS classification proposed by the ACR - American College of Radiology, is most valid but we describe in detail only those changes that we want to be monitored; about the rest, we only mention that they exist and what is their nature, if they are different changes and there are few of them, we describe them all.
6. There are 3 main types of ultrasound imaging - B-mode with image harmonization, color Doppler and elastography; all available methods are used to approximate the biology of the lesion and to decide about diagnosis and treatment.
7. It should be noted that elastography, in assessing the stiffness of the lesion, complements the B-mode examination with an element similar to breast palpation, but allows to draw more far-reaching conclusions (elastography is crucial in differentiating between BIRADS-3 and 4 - in deciding on tissue biopsy).